

ACQUISITION FOREIGN LANGUAGE VIA INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

In teaching foreign language to engineering students is long, complex process as it requires learners to have better known L1 because L1 is a key to acquire FL. It is full understanding linguistics aspects of L1 enable learners to better understand FL. Without intervention of L1 in teaching foreign language, effect will be less, consequently, we should explain translation of FL in native language (Uzbek) in details, otherwise, acquisition of foreign language may be complex, long, and misunderstanding. Besides, teaching languages via computer assisted classes is highly demanding now due to computerization society. This paper deals with the issues focusing on some features of instructions to learn FL with the help of Information technology especially in translation activities. Some scholars stated their expressions on vocabulary acquisition in FL learning and its beneficial traits.

Introduction: Language acquisition is one of the most important and fascinating aspects of human development. There are various subconscious aspects of language development such as met linguistic, conscious, formal teaching of language and acquisition of the written system of language in both L1 and FL. Various language variables are involved in the language processes like phonology, vocabulary, morphology, syntax, paralinguistic, pragmatics and discourse. In order to provide success in cognitive functioning as well as professional life of an individual, his/her first language acquisition must develop strongly in the early years. The characteristics of language learning entails the successful mastery of steadily accumulating structural entities and organizing this knowledge into coherent structures which lead to effective communication in the target language if this is the case, than we would expect that well-formed accurate and complete target language structures would one after another, emerge on the learner's path towards eventual mastery of the language. Second language learners appear to accumulate structural entities of the target language but demonstrate difficulty in organizing this knowledge in appropriate, coherent structures. There appears to be a significant gap between the accumulation and the organization of the knowledge. Moreover, in teaching and learning second language, we often encounter with unavoidable technical language which is difficult to paraphrase and guess, therefore, our learners should learn vocabulary in order to express his/her ideas by extending their horizons of knowledge in engineering in English language.

Acquisition of linguistic skills through interference of L1

When reading and writing and speaking the target language (FL), ESP learners tend to rely on their native language (L1) structures to produce a response. If the structures of the two languages are distinctly different, then one could expect relatively high frequency of errors to occur in L2, thus indicating an interference of L1 on FL [2]. Furthermore, extensive research has already been done in the area of native language interference on the target language. Dulay [1] defined interference as the automatic transfer, due to habit, of the surface structure of the first language onto surface of the target language but Lott [3,265] stated that interference as “errors «in the learner’s use of the language that can be traced back to the mother tongue. Ellis [2,51] refers to interference as “transfer”, he stated that the influence that the learner’s L1 exerts over the acquisition of an FL. He argued that the transfer is governed by learners’ perceptions what is transferable and by their stage of development in FL learning. In learning a target language, learners instruct their own internal rules with the use of their L1 knowledge, but only when they believe it will help them in the learning task or when they have become sufficiently proficient in the FL for transfer to be possible. Ellis raises the need to distinguish between errors and mistakes and makes an important distinction between the two. He says that errors reflect gaps in the learner’s knowledge; they occur because the learner does not what is correct.

Mistakes reflect occasional lapses in performance; they occur because in a particular instance, the learner is unable to perform what he or she knows. It appears much more difficult for an adult to learn a second language system that is as well learned as the first language. Thomas [9] argued that we should try to understand how people communicate effectively with the linguistic resources available to them. Ellis [5] also points to the fact that explicit instruction improves the speed of acquisition, the need for input in FL acquisition has been recognized widely, and that the input that learners are receiving in the form of their language instruction has significant effects on their learning asset.

The National Reading Panel [6] concluded that a combination of both direct and indirect methods is the best method for teaching vocabulary; direct instruction, which promotes word consciousness, involves a focus on roots and affixes, word play, and word orders. It is also believed that restructuring tasks and recycling new vocabulary throughout the course enhances vocabulary development. Graves [8] also advocates a kind of fostering word consciousness. Stahl [7] stated that vocabulary instruction must include both definitional and contextual information regarding the meaning of each word. Texas Reading Initiative [10] suggests using descriptions, interesting metaphors, similes, and plays on words, and explaining the contexts of use to be useful techniques of consciousness-raising when teaching new words.

Mastering second language

Nunan found that language use opportunities and successful communication are dependent upon the mastery of FL vocabulary. Therefore, pupils should learn and acquire a sufficient amount of vocabulary to fully engage in verbal communication. The communicative process of negotiation promotes second language comprehension and the type of task that is normally involved emulates the information gap format to push learners to communicate in classrooms. Additionally, it has also been suggested that negotiated interaction promotes FL vocabulary acquisition in terms of retention; whereby language learners will have to ability to hold the vocabulary for short-term and long-term retrieval in their memories – with particular reference to nouns. While translating authentic texts in classes, we use L1 knowledge which improves the comprehension skills of learners. For example, for the students in transport engineering:

1. The vehicles got bigger and heavier and more powerful and as such they were eventually capable of pulling a train of many cars filled with freight and passengers. Many attempts had been made in England by the 1830's to develop a practical vehicle that didn't need rails.
2. The use of fuel cell promises a reduction in environmental pollution from car exhaust emissions, and the end of our dependence on oil for fuel.
3. The engineering difficulties were great mainly because much of the soil was composed of running sand. Fortunately, most of the running sand lay close to the surface, therefore it was found possible to use out-and-cover method of construction under many streets

Conclusion

Teaching languages to engineering students is not easy but complex, and long-learning process because they do not only learn language but also subject matter in L2. Teaching foreign language for specific purposes mainly is content-based, we often teach them authentic context both in written and spoken forms so as enable them better acquire FL. However, they sometimes encounter with issues while reading contexts, not having enough knowledge in L1, that's why we often use L1 in order to introduce them new data about their specialty. Therefore, native language is essential in acquisition of second language in language classes. More practice may gave them more meaning in engineering in L1 and FL.

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